

DYSPHEMISM AS MAIN TOOL OF “HATE SPEECH”**Vepkhvadze Tamar**

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***Abstract.** A set of euphemisms, orthophemisms and dysphemisms is called X-phemisms (Allan, Burridge 1988. Euphemism, dysphemism, and cross-varietal synonymy:10). The use of X-phemisms is a common linguistic phenomenon almost in all languages. They are used in everyday conversation, as well as in media discourse. By using X-phemisms, you can express your thoughts formally, usually politely and informally. In communication, people frequently find themselves in situations where they are unable to express themselves straightforwardly; consequently, they resort to euphemisms. They use orthophemisms to express common or formal ideas, and dysphemisms to express direct and offensive ideas. All of them are used in media discourse; their choice is determined by a variety of factors, including location, time, goal, participants, and topic of the conversation. In other words, the participants of the conversation may use direct, indirect or common expressions in their everyday speech.*

Euphemism is the substitution of rude, negative or offensive words and expressions for more delicate and generally, more positive expressions.

Dysphemism, the opposite term, on the other hand, is the substitution of a positive or neutral words with negative, unpleasant or offensive words.

Dysphemisms are the opposites of euphemisms in that they give a (strong) negative meaning to a detonate and are geared toward having a negative impact.

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Dysphemisms are used to degrade and humiliate a person. When a speaker uses this method, he or she uses directly expressed forms addressed to a specific group or a listener. Dysphemisms are frequently used in literary texts, political speeches and everyday conversation. The goal of our report was to identify the peculiarities of the use of dysphemisms in modern media discourse and to analyze their semantic, structural and pragmatic peculiarities. The goal of the research was to consider the theoretical problems of modern studies of euphemisms and dysphemisms. Consequently, the question of the study was where euphemisms and dysphemisms are most commonly used in media discourse. The paper uses methods of analogy and typological study, and semantic-pragmatic analysis.

In recent years, mass media has shown a steady development, and media representatives try to impress listeners using individual methods. The method used by an author to make an impression on the reader makes a difference. One way is to use euphemisms and dysphemism in printed media discourse, giving a listener a positive or negative outlook of a particular event, object or action. Newspaper articles wield political power through word-choice tactics and strategies. We frequently encounter such scenes in the political realm, when a person attempts to disguise reality with a euphemism, and aims to express negative attitude, reveal

actions of other people, or criticize the actions of government representatives and politicians by using dysphemisms.

Quite often, the purpose of dysphemism is to blame someone. Politicians use dysphemisms in printed media to humiliate people.

In political texts, discrediting a governmental authority with accusation and mockery is intended to offend and humiliate it.

Humiliation is often realized through invective; on the other hand, humiliation may be not only a rude word, but also non-standard vocabulary, and thus, a greater effect is achieved. Humiliation can be addressed directly to the object or indirectly, through evaluation of the object.

Thus, dysphemisms and euphemisms are tactic linguistic tactics used to achieve a desirable pragmatic effect in mass media. In political texts, discreditation realized by means of such tactics as humiliation, accusations and mockery, on the one hand, aims at humiliating and discrediting a person, and disclosing the actions of the authorities and mocking them, on the other hand. All of this is possible with dysphemisms as well as euphemisms. Dysphemisms and euphemisms are used with negative and neutral meanings, i.e., they acquire negative perception in a specific context. They are used for mockery, and thus have an ironic character.

Dysphemisms are intended to give rise to different feelings and emotions. Dysphemisms are used in all aspects of our everyday lives, and aim at strengthening the speaker's influence on the listener. People use dysphemisms to express negative emotions. Dysphemisms aggravate the situation and humiliate the addressee. Discreditation, which is most common in political discourse, is one of the functions of dysphemisms.

If a speaker uses dysphemisms to (generally) irritate or offend people during his/her conversation, he/she wants to humiliate and abuse a listener. Any humiliating comment addressed to others with the intent to humiliate or harm the listeners is dysphemistic. Dysphemisms have the potential to cause conflicts.

Dysphemisms describe hierarchy of social relations within a society, and currently, the struggle against political correctness is considered as most tabooed. This is particularly true with the category of dysphemisms used in the field of national affiliation, which clearly demonstrates sensitivity of the feeling of national identity in today's multicultural world. Reckless expressions towards any nation may have severe consequences: in some developed countries, such public expressions are fined. Anyway, there is always a reason for a speaker to use a dysphemism mostly arising from an acute emotion. The pragmatics of its use vary depending on the speaker's intention, or the concrete and contextual discourse situation.

The classification of dysphemism encompasses all aspects of public life, including political, religious, ethnic, gender, sexual, racist, criminalist, economic, social, and cultural ones.

Dysphemisms are often used with people with psychic and physical disabilities, what is the sign of the lack of the society's empathy to them, while the intentional use of dysphemisms violates norms for tabooed denotations.

In all cases that lead us to the connotative meaning of the word, speakers' annoyance is the case as a result of use of these expressions. Nevertheless, it is not advisable to use them in such communicative situations because they contradict the filling of the vocabulary and the tone of statements.

The main goal of the modern linguistic community is not social prohibition of euphemisms and dysphemisms, but prohibition of tabooed vocabulary units in

specific communicative-pragmatic situations. Consequently, the most important parameters are the goal of communication, role, and personal relations (attitude) among the communicants, who regulate their own communicative interests using euphemisms and dysphemisms.

Keywords: *dysphemism, euphemism, hate speech, media discourse*

A set of euphemisms, orthophemisms and dysphemisms is called X-phemisms (Allan, Burridge 1988. Euphemism, dysphemism, and cross-varietal synonymy:10). The use of X-phemisms is a common linguistic phenomenon almost in all languages. They are used in everyday conversation, as well as in media discourse. By using X-phemisms, you can express your thoughts formally, usually politely and informally. In communication, people frequently find themselves in situations where they are unable to express themselves straightforwardly; consequently, they resort to euphemisms. They use orthophemisms to express common or formal ideas, and dysphemisms to express direct and offensive ideas. All of them are used in media discourse; their choice is determined by a variety of factors, including location, time, goal, participants, and topic of the conversation. In other words, the participants of the conversation may use direct, indirect or common expressions in their everyday speech.

There are a variety of means to express oneself. Allan and Burridge distinguish between *privileged* and *unprivileged* modes of language expression. They attribute orthophemisms (neutral words and expressions. The term was coined by Allan and Burridge and was first used by the authors in the book “Forbidden Words” in 2006), and euphemisms to the former, and dysphemisms to the latter category. The unprivileged method also implies the use of kakophemisms (intentionally used offensive words and expressions).

Both dysphemisms and kakophemisms are distinguished by rude speech, but there is a slight difference between them. A dysphemism can be offensive or simply a humorous reprimand, whereas a kakophemism is typically an intentional offence. Cacophemistic language is used to replace neutral words in a harsh, offensive, rude, and vulgar manner. Some words are extremely vulgar but not entirely obscene (that is, not entirely tabooed in decent society). These are offensive but not shocking words.

Accordingly, dysphemisms, malfemisms, euphemisms, and kakophemisms are words and expressions deliberately used to make effect.

Euphemism is the substitution of rude, negative or offensive words and expressions for more delicate and generally, more positive expressions. Dysphemism, the opposite term, on the other hand, is the substitution of a positive or neutral words with negative, unpleasant or offensive words.

Hugh Rawson divides euphemisms into two categories: positive and negative euphemisms (Rawson, 1998: 492). As an example of positive euphemisms he cites invented, ennobled names of some profession as a sign of solidarity with a member of society. Such euphemisms are, for example, “stylist” instead of “hairdresser” or “barber,” “office assistant” or “administrative assistant” instead of “secretary,” etc.

Most euphemisms are negative. Their purpose is to spare the addressee, to convey negative, unpleasant or undesirable information in milder forms. Examples of such words and word combinations in the Georgian language are: “is gone” instead of “died”, “behind the bars” instead of “imprisoned”, “under the weather” instead of “drunk,” “overweight” instead of “fat,” etc.

According to K. Jorjanelli, a euphemism is defined as follows: “A word (or expression) used as a substitute for a word (or expression) that is considered

dangerous, disagreeable, rude, offensive, or unjustified in a given language group is referred to as a euphemism. Euphemisms and the words (or expressions) they replace refer to the same objective data. They differ in that they make different impressions on the listener” (Jorjaneli, 1977: 11).

Dysphemisms are the opposites of euphemisms in that they give a strong negative meaning to a detonate and are geared toward having a negative impact.

The term “dysphemism” has an offensive connotation. It is used to condemn a specific aspect of an event. Dysphemism is “a violation of polite rules” (Allan, Burridge 2006. *Forbidden Words: Taboo and the Censoring of Language*: 11).

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In recent years, mass media has shown a steady development, and media representatives try to impress listeners using individual methods. The method used by an author to make an impression on the reader makes a difference. One way is to use euphemisms and dysphemism in printed media discourse, giving a listener a positive or negative outlook of a particular event, object or action. Newspaper articles wield political power through word-choice tactics and strategies. We frequently encounter such scenes in the political realm, when a person attempts to disguise reality with a euphemism, and aims to express negative attitude, reveal

actions of other people, or criticize the actions of government representatives and politicians by using dysphemisms.

Using dysphemisms, the society tries to reveal the actions of different persons, or to reprimand state representatives or politicians, while euphemisms serve an opposite purpose trying to express the harsh reality in milder forms.

Quite often, the purpose of dysphemism is to blame someone. Politicians use dysphemisms in printed media to humiliate people. The wordings of printed or social media platforms use the following types of dysphemisms:

1) Neutral words turn into insulting or derogatory words.

2) Dysphemisms are used to create a negative attitude to an event and emphasize the extremity of an event. Such cases are particularly frequent in politics.

3) Dysphemisms are used to ignore political correctness, being particularly true with the politicians, who often resort to dysphemisms in conversation.

4) Discreditation - can be viewed one of the main types of dysphemisms.

5) Emphasis – an example is a speaker wishing to emphasize negative aspects of a person or event, and resorting to dysphemisms to this end. The example given below illustrates the outrageous behavior of government officials.

6) Accusation - accusing someone by using dysphemisms to create a negative effect.

7) Aggravating facts and events.

In a political context, discrediting a governmental authority with accusation and mockery is intended to offend and humiliate it.

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thus, a greater effect is achieved. Humiliation can be addressed directly to the object or indirectly, through evaluation of the object.

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In all cases that lead us to the connotative meaning of the word, speakers' annoyance results from the use of these expressions. Nevertheless, it is not advisable to use them in such communicative situations because they contradict the filling of the vocabulary and the tone of statements.

The practice of linguistic ethics is particularly important in a civilized society. After all, speech, along with other factors, shapes human culture. The domain of linguistic ethics incorporates such units as euphemisms. Changes in ethical norms can be seen in the language, as language changes as the society develops. A number of studies of the relationship between language and culture show that globalization has an impact on the development of both society and language. Many things that were once considered unethical are now supported and less perceived as unacceptable.

Considering the foregoing, it is clear that dysphemism is the primary semantic tool of hate speech.

According to a 1997 recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe, hate speech includes all forms of expression that advocate,

incite, promote or justify racial hatred, xenophobia, anti-Semitism or other forms of hostility based on intolerance, including nationalism, ethnocentrism, and discrimination against minorities or migrants.

The standard for regulating hate speech varies from country to country: while hate speech is a criminal offense in most EU countries, the American legal system, it is protected by absolute privilege, except where there is a clear, immediate and imminent threat of violence.

Hate speech is not criminalized in Georgia either, unless there is an obvious and immediate danger.

Only broadcasters are subject to hate speech restrictions prohibiting airing programs that aim to insult or discriminate against a person or group based on their physical ability, ethnicity, religion, worldview, gender, sexual orientation, or other characteristics or statuses, or to emphasize such status. The only exceptions are when it is required by the program content and is intended to highlight existing animosity.

Nonetheless, media world in Georgia is saturated with hate speech addressed to the society's most vulnerable groups, namely minorities and political opponents. However, it should be noted that hate speech in Georgia has its own history. The verbal form of hatred was deeply ingrained in Soviet Georgia in the 1920-1930s, where hatred was usually motivated by class struggle. What fuels hatred in modern-day Georgia, and what are its Soviet roots?

Quite often, hate speech is used to prepare for violence, as mentioned in the public lecture "Hate speech in the printed media of Soviet Georgia in the 1920-30s" given by Giorgi Kekelidze, the director of the National Library of Georgia on December 11, 2021 in the conference hall of the Library.

“Red terror to the nobility, the Mensheviks, and other of our enemies! Death, contempt and merciless judgment to the Menshevik bandits! Whoever is not with us is our enemy!” (quote) - Giorgi Kekelidze took this excerpt from a September 1924 newspaper. The caricatures printed in the newspaper “Musha” (“The Worker”) were also full of hatred and threats of reprisals: for example, one of them depicts a worker smashing the 6 percent painted on the wall: “The numbers of the different strata of society changed in terms of percentage, and those people who might be in the minority were equally doomed to be scolded, cursed, exiled to Siberia, and shot in the worst case. For example, a worker in one of the posters says: “Wow, 6% of the nobility – that’s unbelievable! They will gobble up all Georgia! Let me reduce the number of these parasites in my own way” (quote).

According to Giorgi Kekelidze, the Soviet press, filled with hate speech, was one of the tools that prepared the repressions of the 1930s. Accusations in the newspaper often meant imprisonment or even death penalty.

Hate speech was also introduced to the press by the state itself, because the winning power believed that all who were different should be destroyed. According to Lasha Bakradze, director of Georgian Museum of Literature (interview with Radio Liberty), the hate speech used by the modern Georgian media did not emerge from nothing:

“Of course, we are still a part of this Soviet heritage, and have not gone too far. There are no limitations or barrier in Georgia for a person to refrain from the language we call hate speech. The objects of hatred is the same stratum of people as before, in the 1930s, i.e. those who are perceived by some group as an enemy, alien, or unacceptable“ (quote).

In Georgia, hate speech is used frequently and almost everywhere, both in personal or public domain. Television broadcasts and social media platforms are overflowed with hate speech.

A particularly aggressive form of hate speech is used by the media against sexual minorities, and homophobic statements are usually heard regarding the corruption of the country, the degeneration of the Georgians, and the fight against Orthodoxy. However, as David Mchedlidze, the editor of the online portal MEDIA.GE, noted in his interview with Radio Liberty, hate speech is commonly used against ethnic and religious minorities: “Sometimes the media is a provoking factor in encouraging hate speech. One might say that there are a number of media sources not only using hate speech, but preach hatred as well, and propaganda attacks are quite common. As an example, let us recall May 17, 2013, when an action against sexual minorities was held. This was preceded by the relevant propaganda both on the Internet and in the printed media” (quote).

The Media Development Foundation published a media monitoring report titled “Hate Speech - Xenophobia” in 2015. The report was prepared by the Media Development Foundation as part of the UN Georgia Association’s project “Strengthening National Integration in Georgia,” which was funded by the US Agency for International Development (USAID). The report sought to identify sources of hate speech, xenophobia, homophobia, gender discrimination, stereotypes, and anti-Western sentiments in the media and public discourse, as well as to investigate the extent to which news sources adhere to professional standards when covering the aforementioned topics. The study covered a one-year period (February 17, 2014-February 18, 2015) and aimed to identify sources of hate speech and discrimination on various grounds.

It should be noted that in the context of the hate speech propagation, the report looked at examples of different groups such as: media, political parties, acting and former government officials, clergy, and other members of the general public. The many examples and gathered visual materials show that dysphemism is a major tool of hate speech.

The report also provides numerous examples of how context or mood can transform a neutral word into a tool for inciting hatred. The examples given in the report demonstrate that euphemisms and dysphemisms form a linguistic dichotomy. The common basis for the dichotomy is: 1) the general linguistic mechanism of formation - paraphrase; 2) the cognitive component of the meaning of the original and derived names (euphemisms and dysphemisms) is maintained; and 3) the original and resulting names differ at the level of the pragmatic component of meaning.

At the heart of the controversy are: 1) the opposite orientation of the emotional and evaluative qualification of the meaning (euphemism - charged positively, dysphemism - generating negative connotations, charged negatively); 2) Generation and use of euphemisms and dysphemisms is due to the intent of the addressee, which aims to achieve the opposite pragmatic effect, in particular, to neutralize a negative pragmatic effect with a euphemism and amplify a negative, pragmatic effect with a dysphemism.

Euphemisms and dysphemisms of a lexical unit occur at the level of speech and are not a linguistic feature of a word itself. Euphemisms and dysphemisms qualify only in a certain context, and when its parameters change, there is a dissolution of euphemisms or dysphemisms of words. Assuming that a lexical unit is regularly reproduced as a euphemism, it is recorded in lexicographic sources.

Adhering to ethical norms is important in a developed society. As B. Jorbenadze points out, language etiquette, which is close to euphemistic expressions in its essence, belongs to the domain of ethics (Jorbenadze 1997: 76). Language, among other things, shows the level of culture of a society. Therefore, language etiquette is intertwined with many aspects of human life. According to Wilhelm Humboldt's concept, language is a worldview; language is the direct expression of the nation's soul; learning a new language is the acquisition of a new worldview. This concept sparked interest in the study of language in relation to thinking, consciousness, and culture (Jorbenadze 1997: 11). The presence of euphemisms in language is an affirmation of the connection between the language and the societal culture. Euphemism is not an accidental phenomenon of a language, but has psycholinguistic and ethnopsychological grounds, and is linked to the worldview, psychology, history and culture of a nation. In a cultured society, the norms of ethics are more sophisticated, and hence, more refined linguistic ethics, because language is the primary tool to express human thoughts.

Ethical standards are quite substantial, what, among other things, implies the rules of social behavior and language etiquette, expressed by various euphemisms depending on the motives dictating it (taboo, hierarchy, politeness...); thus, etiquette is a set of norms of behavior, and language etiquette is the sum of linguistic units used by people to adhere to the specific rules of behavior.

Thus, language etiquette includes euphemism in a broad sense. A euphemism is a linguistic unit used to maintain "its appearance" under different (hierarchical, politeness, belief, convincing...) principles. It is the same eloquence that has a function with positive connotations, adorned with a polite-expressive grammatical inventory or lexical units to convince/charm the listener, to maintain

“appearance” and to complete a successful communicative act. It has a certain stylistic function and distribution across various genres of texts.

Overall, the main goal of the modern linguistic community is not social prohibition of euphemisms and dysphemisms, but prohibition of tabooed vocabulary units in specific communicative-pragmatic situations. Consequently, the most important parameters are the goal of communication, role, and personal relations (attitude) among the communicants, who regulate their own communicative interests using euphemisms and dysphemisms.

References:

1. Allan K., Burrige K. (1988). Euphemism, dysphemism, and cross-varietal synonymy: School of communication, arts and critical enquiry. Cambridge Univ. Press.
2. Allan K., Burrige K. (2006). Forbidden Words: Taboo and the Censoring of Language: Cambridge Univ. Press.
3. Media Monitoring Report (2015). The Language of Hate - Xenophobia. Tbilisi: Media Development Foundation.
4. Rawson, H. (1998). Euphemisms. In: G. Goshgarian (Ed.), Exploring Language. 8th ed., USA: Addison-Wesley Educational Publishers Inc.
5. Jorbenadze B. (1997). Language and Culture. Tbilisi: Publishing House “Georgian Language”.
6. Jorjaneli K. (1977). Euphemisms and Verbal Taboos. Monographic study. Tbilisi: Tbilisi University Press.